

Europe-LAND cards and Success Stories for modelling tools

Complementing the deliverable D4.1 “Databases of existing LU/LC patterns and spatial modelling tools” we provide user-friendly, hands-on guidance tools for selected models/modelling tools for environmental domains related to the project focus in the form of compact information cards, and related success stories that illustrate how the respective model can be applied in both research and practice. These tools are provided for five environmental domains covering LULC, Climate, Hydrology, Forest, and Biodiversity (see Tables 1 –5).

Cards for modelling tools

For modelling tools each of five above mentioned domains key environmental standardized model cards were developed to summarise the model technical, functional, and practical characteristics. The purpose of the modelling card is to provide a concise and accessible overview that facilitates comparison across models.

Each card includes key details such as the model’s full name, developer/institution, year/version, software environment (e.g., TerrSet, R, QGIS, Python), and modelling principles (e.g., rule-based, stochastic, machine learning). It also details the types of input data required (e.g., land cover maps, drivers like slope or population density), core modelling capabilities, and scenario development functions. In addition to technical information, the cards highlight intended users (e.g., planners, academics, NGOs), hardware and software requirements, and extensions or plug-ins if applicable. Where helpful, we included a schematic diagram of the modelling process and links to online documentation or tutorials.

These cards serve as essential open access reference tools for users seeking to understand or apply LUCC models in research or planning, and are especially useful for selecting a model based on project needs, data availability, or spatial scale.

Success Stories for modelling tools

The cards are further complemented by selected success stories based on open access scientific papers that showcase its practical application in a European and selected non-European case studies. These stories were extracted from recent high-quality peer-reviewed publications and are meant to illustrate how each model has been effectively used to simulate or analyse land change in real-world settings.

The success stories include essential details such as the study area (e.g., Romania, Hungary, Italy), the modelling timeframe, the types of land cover analysed, and the goals of the project (e.g., predicting deforestation, assessing urban sprawl, evaluating climate-related land change). Furthermore, each success story summarises the modelling process (e.g., calibration methods, transition rules, scenario assumptions), validation results (e.g., Kappa, ROC, FOM), and policy or management implications.

For example, the CLUE-S model was used in Romania to predict forest cover until 2050 under different scenarios, providing actionable insights for forest management and carbon sequestration. SECLAND model in Austria to project future land-use until 2050 under climate and socioeconomic change in the LTSER region Eisenwurzen.

These narratives not only demonstrate the strengths and limitations of each model but also enhance understanding of their real-world utility, guiding future users in how to design and implement LUCC modelling projects effectively.

A summary of the included modelling tools and their key characteristics is provided in tables 1 –5.

Table 1. Overview and key characteristics of LULC models

Model	Use of LULC	Suitable For
CA-Markov (Cellular Automata–Markov Chain)	Uses transition probabilities and neighbourhood rules to simulate spatial dynamics	Urban expansion, deforestation, and long-term LU/LC trends
CLUE-S (Conversion of Land Use & Effects – Small scale)	Spatial allocation model combining demand with statistical suitability maps	Regional/national scenario-based land use projections
GEOMOD (Geographic Modelling System)	Predicts land change with logistic regression and suitability maps	Simple land use prediction with limited data requirements
LCM-Climate (Land Change Modeler with Climate)	Integrates LULC transitions with climate variables	Coupled land–climate studies, mitigation/adaptation
LSTM (neural net)	Deep learning model using past land cover and drivers	Data-driven LULC prediction with high spatio-temporal accuracy
MOLUSCE (Modules for Land Use Change Evaluation)	Uses multiple ML algorithms plus CA for transitions	Urban dynamics, spatio-temporal modelling, scenario analysis
SEC-LAND (Socio-Ecosystem Change)	Spatially explicit scenario modelling of socio-ecological systems	Participatory scenario development, landscape transitions
SLEUTH (Slope, Land use, Exclusion, Urban extent, Transportation, Hillshade)	CA model using physical parameters to model urban growth	Historical trend-calibrated urban expansion
FLUS (Future Land Use Simulation)	Integrates human/environmental drivers in CA framework	Scenario analysis, sustainable land-use strategy development

Table 2. Overview and key characteristics of included climate models

Model	Focus	Suitable For	LULC Effect on Outputs
JULES (Joint UK Land Environment Simulator)	Represents land use change via Plant Functional Types (PFTs)	Land surface interactions in Earth system models	Alters energy, carbon, nitrogen, and water fluxes
LPJ-GUESS (Lund-Potsdam-Jena General Ecosystem Simulator)	Simulates vegetation dynamics and land management	Ecosystem dynamics, climate and land-use impact studies	Influences biogeochemical cycles, water balance, vegetation
MEGAN (Model of Emissions of Gases and Aerosols from Nature)	Requires vegetation types and LAI for emissions modelling	Biogenic emissions, atmospheric chemistry, air quality	Affects emissions of isoprene, BVOCs, aerosols
ORCHIDEE (Organizing Carbon and Hydrology in Dynamic Ecosystems)	Maps LULC to PFTs and includes land use change dynamics	Carbon, nitrogen and water cycling; Earth system modelling	Drives fluxes of carbon, water, and energy
GCAM (Global Change Analysis Model)	Detailed LULC component; models land allocation and changes	IAMs, climate-energy-land policy assessments	Impacts emissions, energy, food, land, water sectors
CLM (Community Land Model)	Uses sub-grid land units and PFTs, includes urban and managed lands	Land surface simulations in CESM; biogeochemical processes	Impacts surface fluxes, water, energy, carbon
Biome-BGC (Biogeochemical Cycles Model)	Uses site and land cover parameters for PFT-specific simulations	Ecosystem productivity, climate change impact, biogeochemical fluxes	Affects GPP, NPP, ET, LAI, NEE etc.
WRF (Weather Research and Forecasting Model)	Includes urban canopy models and land surface processes	Weather prediction, regional climate, air quality, urban climate	Influences heat island effect, rainfall, wind fields
REMO (Regional Climate Model)	Couples with land surface models and includes LULC dynamics	Regional climate simulations, high-resolution impact modelling	Affects rainfall, evapotranspiration, hydrological feedback
RegCM (Regional Climate Model)	Supports land surface schemes (e.g. CLM, BATS), models LU change	Regional downscaling, climate impact studies, CORDEX	Alters land-atmosphere feedbacks and surface climate
DANUBIA (Modular Environmental Simulation Framework)	Includes detailed land use data for spatially explicit scenario analysis	Water governance, land-use/climate interaction, socio-environmental modelling	Affects water demand, hydrological processes, and land management responses

Table 3. Overview and key characteristics of included hydrological models

Model	Focus	Suitable For	LULC Effect on Outputs
SWAT (Soil & Water Assessment Tool)	Uses land use data for hydrological simulation	Basin-scale water quantity and quality	Changes in land cover affect runoff, erosion, nutrients
PRECIS (Providing REgional Climates for Impacts Studies)	Uses LULC for downscaling boundaries	Regional climate impact assessments	Alters localised climate variables (rainfall, extremes)
EPIC (Erosion-Productivity Impact Calculator)	Integrates land management and crop rotations	Field-scale crop yield, soil, and erosion	Land use changes affect irrigation, runoff, and erosion
MIKE SHE	Integrates land cover into coupled surface-groundwater processes	Integrated surface-groundwater watershed modelling	Land use influences evapotranspiration, infiltration, runoff
VIC (Variable Infiltration Capacity)	Uses LULC in surface-water parameterisation	Large-scale hydrological modelling	Land cover changes affect soil moisture and streamflow
HBV (Hydrologiska Byråns Vattenbalansavdelning)	Integrates LULC in runoff simulation	Catchment water balance and streamflow	LULC changes influence runoff and flow patterns
TOPMODEL	Uses LULC in topography-driven hydrology	Saturated groundwater flow and runoff	Land cover affects soil moisture distribution and runoff
HEC-HMS (Hydrologic Modelling System)	Uses LULC for flow simulations	Flood forecasting and water resources management	Land use changes affect runoff volume and flood peaks
RHESSys (Regional Hydro-Ecologic Simulation System)	Integrates LULC in ecohydrological processes	Integrated carbon-water dynamics at catchment scale	LULC changes influence evapotranspiration, runoff, nutrients

Table 4. Overview and key characteristics of included forest modelling tools

Model	Focus	Suitable For	LULC Effect on Outputs
iLand (forest LANDscape and disturbance)	Forest landscape dynamics and disturbance	Resilience, biodiversity, ecosystem services	Changes in land use alter regeneration, carbon storage, fire spread, diversity
LANDIS-II (LANDscape Disturbance & Succession)	Forest succession and disturbance modelling	Policy evaluation, forest planning	LULC shapes disturbance spread, species mix, age structure
3-PG (Physiological Principles Predicting Growth)	Forest growth and productivity	Yield modelling, carbon accounting	Land use shifts growth potential, productivity and carbon fluxes
FORMIND (Forest Model for INdividual-based Dynamics)	Tree competition in tropical forests	Tropical forest management, climate change	Affects biomass recovery, species composition, regeneration capacity
SORTIE-ND (Spatially Explicit Individual-based Forest Dynamics)	Tree-level spatial dynamics	Fine-scale forest ecology	Land cover influences species coexistence and succession dynamics
ForClim (Forest succession & climate change model)	Forest succession and climate impacts	Temperate forest development, climate impacts	Land cover influences long-term species composition and structure
EFISCEN (European Forest Information Scenario model)	Forest resource projections	Policy scenarios, wood supply	LULC changes affect harvestable wood and age dynamics
PICUS (Patch model for forest dynamics)	Spatially explicit patch-based dynamics	Forest structure and biodiversity studies	Land cover affects regeneration, competition, growth heterogeneity
CARAIB (CARbon Assimilation in the Biosphere)	Vegetation–climate interactions	Global carbon and water flux modelling	LULC changes impact carbon, water, and energy fluxes
FORMOSAIC (Forest mosaic dynamics simulator)	Spatio-temporal forest dynamics	Disturbance dynamics, succession	Land cover determines gap dynamics, succession, and diversity
ForestGALES (Forest GALE and windthrow model)	Wind damage risk assessment	Windthrow vulnerability, management	LULC influences exposure, damage extent, and stability

Table 5. Overview and key characteristics of included biodiversity modelling tools for species and ecosystem assessments

Model (Name)	Focus	Suitable For	LULC Effect on Outputs
MaxEnt (Maximum Entropy)	Species distribution modelling (SDM)	Species range predictions, conservation planning	LULC shifts predicted habitat suitability and ranges
BIOMOD2 (R package)	Ensemble species distribution models	Biodiversity forecasting, conservation	LULC determines habitat availability and affects accuracy
InVEST (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services)	Ecosystem services and habitat quality	Land-use planning, trade-off analysis	Land-use patterns drive habitat fragmentation and quality
GLOBIO (Global Biodiversity Model)	Biodiversity intactness (Mean Species Abundance)	Global biodiversity policy support (e.g., IPBES)	Reduced habitat lowers biodiversity intactness
AIM-biodiversity (Asia-Pacific Integrated Model)	Global/regional biodiversity under future scenarios	Scenario analysis, extinction risk assessment	Land-use changes drive species loss and extinction risk
SAR Models (Species–Area Relationship)	Empirical species-area predictions	Estimating species loss from habitat conversion	Habitat loss leads to proportional species extinction
Madingley (General Ecosystem Model)	Trait-based ecosystem model	Global ecosystem structure and function forecasts	Land cover change alters habitat and trophic energy flows
RangeShifter	Spatially explicit dispersal and demography	Species range-shift simulations, connectivity planning	Fragmentation and land cover change affect dispersal
PREDICTS (Projecting Responses of Ecological Diversity in Changing Terrestrial Systems)	Global impacts of land use	Global biodiversity projections, SDG/IPBES/CBD reporting	Changes in land use directly alter species richness, abundance, and intactness
BILBI (Biogeographic Modelling)	Beta-diversity and turnover modelling	Landscape to global-scale diversity assessments	Land cover change shifts community composition and turnover
MOL (Map of Life)	Species distribution and range mapping	Conservation prioritisation and range mapping	LULC change shifts occurrence probabilities and range boundaries